

CONFLICT AND COMMUNITY DEVELOPMENT IN NIGERIA: AN ANALYSIS OF MBIAKONG COMMUNITY IN AKWA IBOM STATE

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ABSTRACT

This study was to examine Conflict and Community Development in Uruan Local Government Area, Akwa Ibom State. Systematic Random Sampling and snowball technique procedures were used to select 196 respondents of 30 years and above in Mbiakong village in Uruan Local Government Area. Physical interviews and observation approaches were used in data collection for this study. The data collected were analysed qualitatively in descriptive way. Majority of the respondents (n = 142/72.4%), reported that youths in the specific area of study were fun of taking arms instead of dialogue to resolve issues and this has always led to communal conflicts. Human Needs Theory (HNT) was employed by the researcher in the study. It was discovered by the researcher that the recent Mbiakong conflict which was the major study of this research work revealed that Uruan people lost a lot of resources during conflicts and these hamper community development. The state government through Honourable Aniekan Basse has been involved in peace and conflicts resolution in Uruan Local Government Area. It was concluded that the presence of the Nigerian Army in Uruan Local Government Area will help in maintaining peace in Uruan Local Government Area. The researcher recommended that the people of the study area in Uruan Local Government Area should see how to use dialogue instead of arms in resolving conflicting issues among themselves.

KEYWORDS: Conflict, community development, Mbiakong, and Uruan

INTRODUCTION

As society is organized, each of us at any given moment occupies a particular place giving us more or less prestige (our fellow men, social psychologists call this; our position or status in society). According to Joy (2008) these positions are determined by many factors, including age, place in the family or society, occupation, economic status etc. However, this as a result, may attract jealousy or envy which can equally bring about conflict at some point, which can hinder community or national development. According to Woodman *et al.* (1969) in Agbo and Ezinwa (2004), “conflict is any situation in which there are incompatible goals, cognition or emotions within or between individuals or groups that leads to opposition. Conflicts are bound to arise in any group or society. Even “sweet hearts” experience conflicts likewise an individual or communities. Accordingly, Nwosu (2004) notes that, conflicts are inevitable in any human society, as much as there are class struggle, interest and resources in the society, there is bound to be misunderstanding among groups or between two communities, and some of these misunderstandings do lead to conflict which is a factor that threatens community development.

Furthermore, conflicts are experienced in most communities in recent times leading to killings of a large number of people and destruction of properties as well as hampering community development at some points. Conflict in most rural communities could be the result of differences in perception, beliefs, attitude, interest, culture, background, goals, and unavoidable interdependence communication inadequacies. Apart from the general agreement that conflict involves disagreement, contradiction, or incompatibility, the concepts remains one of those concepts that are not given to easy, straightforward and generally acceptable definition.

In spite of this, can it be said that conflict as one of the human attributes favours or threatens community and national development? What are the effects of conflict on the human society? Or what measures should be taken to guard against conflicting issues in our society? It is based on these puzzling questions and many others that aroused the curiosity of the researcher to venture into a research of this magnitude in order to critically examine conflict and community development in Akwa Ibom State, using Uruan Local Government Area as the focal point of the study.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

“Conflict is a phenomenon that is an important part of human existence, and a natural part of our daily lives” (Weeks, 1992) in Shedrach (2006). Conflict that takes place within a society may be as a result of several factors. For this reason, in the works of classical social theorists from Marx and Comte to Simmel and Sorel, explanations for social conflict, whether on small or large scale, whether resulting from interactions between social groups or caused by external factors have been an issue of common concern. It may be difficult to point to a single factor as being responsible for maintenance of order within society, it is also difficult to point to a single explanation for the emergence, escalation or protraction of conflict whether violent or otherwise. To Shedrack (2006) “in the case of whether a conflict has degenerated to the point of crisis, it is common that those involved will even find it difficult to remember what led to the initial disagreement”.

With regards to the above views, the human society is characterized by various forms of conflicts and peace threatening phenomena which demands immediate attention by

government, corporate bodies and concerned citizens to device measures to address the impending conflicts challenges posed by social forces that threaten community development efforts. Theoretically, Shedrack (2006) believes that, conflict can be traced to physiological, realist, structural, biological, economic, psycho, cultural, human needs, rational and systematic factors. Consequently, the emergence or escalation of conflict in our communities such as, Mbiakong, Anakpa, Nna-enin, Ndon Ebom, Ekeya Okobo and Ikot Udo-Ikot Anyan communal conflicts in Uruan Local Government Area, Akwa Ibom State caused a lot of damage to human lives and properties as well as hindering community development efforts in the affected communities.

In contemporary times, there are various structures laid down to aid curb any conflicting issue that may lead to mayhem, wars, conflicts, violence and other peaceful-coexistence threatening phenomenon in most communities. These structures include the mass media, public relations activities, campaigns against conflicts, advertising and mobilization on sensitization on the effects of conflict on community development etc. In spite of these structures laid down either by the government, corporate bodies as well as concerned individuals or groups to ensure the avoidance of conflict in our communities, there are still reported cases of community conflicts, communal wars, atrocities, riots, violence and murder in most communities in Akwa Ibom State. Above all, it is based on this premise that this research sought to examine conflict and community development in Akwa Ibom State using Mbiakong community in Uruan Local Government Area, Akwa Ibom State as a case study.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

In conducting this study, the general objective was to examine the influence of conflict on community development in Akwa Ibom State. The specific objectives were:

1. To examine the causes of conflict in Mbiakong and other villages in Uruan Local Government Area
2. To investigate the extent of damages caused by conflicts in Mbiakong and other villages in Uruan Local Government Area

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

In this study, the research carved out the following research questions from the research objectives of the study. These are:

1. What are the causes of conflicts in Mbiakong and other communities in Uruan Local Government Area?
2. What is the extent of damages caused by conflicts in Mbiakong and other villages in Uruan Local Government Area?

LITERATURE REVIEW

Conflict

Conflict as a term, is used usually for the range of arguments, tensions and violent conflicts that occur both within and between states (Burston, 1993). It is therefore defined as the pursuit of incompatible goals or interests by individuals or different groups. This definition by implication, asserts the intrinsic and inevitable nature of conflicts in human life. That is to say, all human or groups of humans have goals and interests which may be different

(as is common in our experience in Uruan Local Government Area and other parts of Akwa Ibom State) with the goals and interests of other groups. Therefore, while conflict is often seen as threat to peace, by itself, it does not necessarily represent a threat to any or all the six types of peace.

Similarly, conflict is experienced recently in our local communities leading to killings, injuries and destruction of properties which equally threaten community development. The escalation of conflict in rural communities equally influence the rate of development in such communities in that it will encourage mass migration as well as other factors that might hinder development in rural communities. The recent communal conflict in Uruan Local Government Area which has claimed many lives and properties is a clear picture of the negative effects of conflict in any society.

According to Shedrack (2006), community conflict is one of the factors that hindered community development due to the level of influence it has on certain developmental oriented projects in the rural communities in Nigeria. Theoretically, the influence of conflict on community development cannot be overemphasized based on the pervading influence it has on the lives of people in the affected community. This can be seen in term of killings and destruction of properties and the environment. According to Shedrack (2006) conflict is an intrinsic and inevitable part of human existence. According to Agbo and Ezinwa (2006) conflict is derived from the Latin Word “configure” which means to strike together. It is clear from the ethnology of the word conflict that there must be a kind of contact for conflict to take place. In other words two things, ideas, feelings, events, persons, beliefs, goals, interest, attitudes and emotion must come in contact or must be literally struck together for conflict to manifest or simply put, there must be an interaction via communication which could be verbal or non-verbal. In the view of Burton (1972) cited in Nwosu (2004) “conflict like sex, is an essential creative element in human relationship, it is the means to change, the means by which our social values of welfare, security, justice and opportunities for personal, group, or community development can be achieved. Indeed, conflict like sex, is to be enjoyed”. As noted earlier from the ethnology of the word conflict, there must be an interaction for conflict to occur. Likewise, there must be an interaction for sexual activity to occur.

Similarly, Hellriegel et al (1969) in Agbo and Ezinwa (2006) observed that, “conflict is any situation in which there are incompatible goals, cognition or emotions within or between individuals or groups that leads to opposition”. Drawing from the above definition, Nwagbara (2004) in Agbo and Ezinwa (2006) deduced three major types of conflict as follows:

1. Goal Conflict: This is a situation in which desired end states or preferred outcome appears to be incompatible.
2. Cognitive Conflict: This is a situation where ideas or thoughts are perceived as incompatible.
3. Affective Conflict: This is also a situation in which feelings or emotions are incompatible; people in this case, literary become angry with one another.

Accordingly, Shedrack (2006) opined that, “it is now widely acceptable that violent conflict is the major hindrance to the development of the African continent”. He further stressed that, “it conflicts human suffering through death, destruction of livelihoods, constant displacement and insecurity”. Conflict as a matter of fact, disrupts the process of production, creates conditions for pillage of the communities' resources and diverts their applications

from development purposes to serving war. Therefore, conflict is thus responsible for perpetuating misery and underdevelopment in most communities the whole world at large. Conflicts have the capacity to severely constraint development endeavours by way of destroying infrastructures, interrupting the production process and diverting resources away from productive users.

Similarly, Shedrack (2006) observed that, “in the Horn of Africa for example, Civil Wars in the 1980s and 1990s hindered development by affecting not only state structures but also other sectors including rural communities”. In three decades, life expectancy went down by 16-20 years, per capita income decreased by 50 percent; famine became endemic; and other welfare indicators such as health and education were worsened. According to World Bank report, (2010) resources diverted away from development use were estimated at \$1 billion a year in Central Africa and more than \$800 million in West Africa. As a result, donors and development agencies have argued that development assistance projects have suffered in many African countries due to incessant conflict in most of the Africa's rural communities. And Akwa Ibom State is not an exception. However, the effects of conflict on community development in Akwa Ibom State are as follows:

1. It leads to claiming of lives and properties;
2. It leads to rural-urban migration which equally encourages over population in major cities in the state;
3. It discourages government and corporate bodies assisted developmental projects in rural communities of Akwa Ibom State;
4. It encourages disunity among people in the state; and
5. It does not support foreign investor to come in, in order to invest in the state which can also help to bring about tremendous development of most rural communities in the state.

Causes of Conflict

According to Nwosu (2004) conflict can arise in some of the following ways:

1. **Goal Incompatibility:** There is bound to be conflict when people pursue different goals that interfere with each other. This kind of conflict is possible at every level and between individuals of different levels or cultural background.
2. **Differentiation:** Differences among individuals as noted earlier is bound to produce conflict. For instance, people with different political orientation, values and background are bound to have conflicting political, social and economic ideology.
3. **Interdependence:** We live in a world where one cannot do without the other, in order to achieve certain goals. Also, in the cause of looking up to a particular individual who may deny us of a helping hand may leads to conflict.
4. **Communication Problem:** A number of conflicts have been attributed to inadequate, poor, or improper communication. For instance, when communication gap is filled with rumour there is bound to be suspicion and misunderstanding which consequently leads to conflict.
5. **Ambiguity over Responsibility or Jurisdiction:** When roles are not clearly defined among individuals or groups, there are bound to be escalation of conflict.
6. **Scarce Resources:** Elementary economics makes it clear that resources are scare when compared with human needs, which is unlimited. Therefore, the competition for these scarce resources automatically brings about conflict among groups,

individuals as well as communities.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

This sub-head presents the theoretical framework of the study. In this study, realist and human needs theories were used to make postulation and generalization based on the variables forming the context of this study.

Human Needs Theory

“The position of human needs theory is similar to that of Frustration-Aggression and Relative Deprivation of resource needs. Its main assumption is that all humans have basic human needs which they seek to fulfill, and that the denial and frustration of these needs by other groups or individuals, as well as community could affect them immediately or later, thereby leading to conflict” (Rosati *et al*, 1990) in Shedrack (2006).

Basic human needs in this sense comprise physical, psychological, social, and spiritual needs. In essence, to provide access to one (e.g. freedom of movement) will amount to denial and could make people to resort to conflict which can consequently bring about destruction of lives and properties by the aggrieved parties. In this regard, it can be seen that community conflict in Uruan Local Government Area, Akwa Ibom State, is due to the denial of one community of one or some of the basic human needs necessary for survival. For instance, Uruan is blessed with good farmlands and rivers for fishing, therefore, the denial of one community from encroaching into another neighbouring village or community to carry out fishing activities may certainly result in conflict. Based on this, it can be right to draw conclusion by marrying the theories that conflict is a threat to community development based on its destructive nature. And on the other hand, it can as well bring about community development if properly managed.

METHODOLOGY

This study was conducted in Mbiakong village in Uruan Local Government Area, Akwa Ibom State. Uruan has three (3) Districts. The districts consist of 41 villages. The 2006 Population Census results indicate that Uruan has a population of about 118, 300 (62, 897 males and 55, 403 females) (aksgov.ng). The local government area is currently sub divided into Northern Uruan, Southern Uruan and Uruan Central. It was selected because of the concern of the researchers on community conflicts which have hampered development in the Mbiakong. Descriptive and exploratory research techniques through interview and participant observation were employed by the researchers for the study. The target population of the study are mature adult from age 30 years and above in Mbiakong village in Uruan Local Government Area. A total of 190 study participants as sample size was derived through Kothari (2004) formula for sample size.

Purposive sampling and snowball techniques were used in selecting only mature adults aged 30 years and above in Mbiakong village in Uruan Local Government Area. In-depth interview still on purposive sampling process was used to select mature women and men to respond to the research questions. Methods of data collection used by the researchers included observations and interview schedule. In observation, the researchers used both participant observation and interviews. The interview schedule contained questions that were unstructured but grouped in sections which the interviewees were expected to provide impartial answers in objective manners. The interviews focused on issues relating to the

causes and effects of conflicts on community development in Mbiakong in Uruan Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. The data collected by the researchers through participant observation and interview schedule were analysed thematically with excerpts.

RESULTS

Causes of Conflicts in Mbiakong community in Uruan Local Government Area

Recently, Mbiakong village has been at the centre of communal crises and armed conflicts in Uruan Local Government Area, Akwa Ibom State. Majority of the interviewed respondents (n = 131/66.8%) in their responses opined that the recent formation of gangs among the youths in Mbiakong who engaged in robbery of market women from Efik land in Cross River State and other neighbouring villages within the first week of July 2017 in Uruan Local Government Area has been the major cause of recent community conflicts in Uruan Local Government Area. It was gathered the researcher that by the researcher that Uruan youths are responsible for causing community conflicts among their villages and Efik people of Cross River State. In the case of Anakpa and Nna-enin, it was gathered that the two villages fought each other over a portion of land which is believed to have been generating good revenue for the Uruan people due to the availability of natural resources. One of the respondents by name Mr Effiong aged 40 years narrated that:

We would have lived in peace in Uruan Local Government area after the Anakpa and Nna-enin crises if some of these useless youths in our village can set their minds on doing something reasonable for themselves instead of robbing people especially innocent women who go about their trading businesses as they did. You will not believe that some irresponsible young men from this our village who called themselves some funny gang names like that, will take their boats in May this year and go to the rivers and wait to rob and rape women that went for their businesses at Nwaniba market through the rivers. When these women returned home their husbands and family members did not hesitate to come and make war against our women and children by killing us the men and get away with our properties. Like in my case, the people went away with my 12 horse power engine boat which cost me N 300,000 (three hundred thousand naira). Now I am left with no other option than to take up my arms and go for the recovery of my 12 horse power boat. What this means is that, the conflict may prolong unless some elders rise up from each village and from among the Efik people to see how we can settle this conflict.

Another respondent aged 43 years and a father of three boys and a business man by name Elder Etim responded in his account that:

It is our youths that are causing problems for us in Mbiakong village. I don't know how these youths have access to guns and sophisticated weapons which they used in robbery and rapping of market women on the sea. You may not believe that young boys can want to rob and rape women who are up to the age of their mothers on the middle of the sea in their boats. Some of them even take the women to the shore after the robbery

and naked them, filmed their nakedness and post it on social media. If you check your facebook you may see what I am talking about. The husbands and family members of these women want to eliminate everybody in this Mbiakong community. That is why the whole of this part of Uruan Local Government Area is facing high degree of conflict now.

Another respondent Mrs. Okon aged 49 narrated her view and experience as follows:

We were experiencing peace in Mbiakong until some gangs of youths arose and engaged in abominable acts, since then this village has been in conflict with other neighbouring villages and as far as Efik across the river. We did not even know what was going on until a day I and my son took my husband boat to go and fetch leaves from the swam forest for Nwaniba market which was to sell the following day. On our way going we started hearing gun shots all over the place and some coming from boats on the river, so I asked my son to paddle to the nearby shore and we escaped for our lives leaving the boat behind. The people came and took our boat away and kill some innocent people. It was later after we met with my husband at the next village that he told me that our youths rob and raped market women on their way from Nwaniba market day. So their husbands have come for revenge. This situation is sad and I hope somebody help us out of this.

One respondent from aged 47 years by name Mrs. Eyo, in her response accounted that;

No other thing is responsible for our community conflicts than our youths. Who will not be angry when he discovered that his wife was not only robbed, but raped and filmed by some young boys for social media publication in facebook and whatsapp? Even as a woman I will not want somebody to do that to me or to someone I know. When the husbands of these women came for revenge as they have troubled us in May, they did not go for the youths who did the wrong to their wives, but they are bringing the revenge on everybody and family in Mbiakong. I wish they can take their guns and killings to the youths where ever they are on the rivers which I heard they lived and operates. One thing is that, the parents of these youths have left Mbiakong for their safety.

Another respondent of age 51 years by name Mr. Oyo in his account on what were the causes of conflicts in Mbiakong and that of Anakpa and Nna-enin villages responded that:

Youths with strange behaviours have rose up in our village from parents you will not expect their children to belong to such groups or gangs. The evil part of it is their activities which are solely responsible for the conflicts we are facing today in Mbiakong. There have been few bad boys who used to operate in our rivers for normal businesses. Suddenly, they began to stop their sand business and indulged in robbing people on transit through our rivers. We have been planning on how to catch them

before they engaged in this terrible crime of robbing and raping market women. What we facing today in Mbiakong is the revenge of the husbands and family members of these market women who were robbed and raped by some hoodlums from this villages in May. The conflict at Anakpa and Nna-enin was due to a portion of land which they have been sharing revenue together until some youths from Anakpa felt that they should owned the place for themselves alone.

The analysis of information gathered by the researcher through interview shows that most of the respondents agreed that the bad activities of youths of Mbiakong village is the major cause of recent conflict in Mbiakong village and other parts of Uruan Local Government Area. Uruan Local Government Area has been facing series of community conflicts majorly caused by the bad activities of Uruan youths. This make Uruan Local Government Area communal conflicts of special interest of study in order to understand why people engage in such activities that do not allow their people to live in peace and plan toward the development of their community.

Damages Caused by Conflicts in Mbiakong Community in Uruan Local Government Area

In communal conflicts, damages are not always quantify or considered during the conflict until the conflict comes to an end, then will those who engaged in such activities begin to count their loses. Most of the interviewed respondents (n = 129/64.3%) in their responses show regrets in Mbiakong conflict with other villages in Uruan Local Government Area. Such damages that include loss of speed boats, houses, family members and businesses were reported by the respondents as the extent of damages caused by the recent communal conflict in Mbiakong-Uruan in May, 2017. One of the respondents aged 44 years, by name Mr. Basseyy narrated:

This crisis in Mbiakong is a recent one in Uruan Local Government Area which took place in May this year 2017 and every time there is conflict in Uruan the people lose lot of things and we lose many of the Uruan people. For instance during between Anakpa and Nna-Enin crises, Uruan people were killed and their properties destroyed in those villages. In this one now in Mbiakong, a lot of properties like houses, boats, businesses have been destroyed and Uruan people have been killed. Every time this thing happens in Uruan, we tend to be going backward instead of progressing. I hope this will stop in Uruan and Uruan will be in peace forever.

Another respondent aged 48 years by name Mr Otu narrated his opinion as follows;
I am a fisherman and I sell sand. I have been feeding myself and my family from our rivers for a long time now. I had two big boats; one 8 horse power boat and the other 12 horse power boat. These two boats cost me about five hundred thousand naira. When this conflict started in May 2017, we did not know that it will escalate into what it is now in Mbiakong. The people went away with my boats and now I have not been doing anything for the past three weeks since this incident took place. We are waiting to see how the problems can be solved so that I can get my

boats back. That was how people lost their lives and properties in Anakpa and Nna-enin in August, last year 2016. I don't know how this will stop in Uruan.

One of the respondents aged 39 years by name Mrs. Okokon responded that; *I am a trader; I used to trade at Ishiet, Ifiayong and Nwaniba Markets here in Uruan. On bloody day which those people came for their revenge, I was on my way to Ishiet market in May 2017. I was interrupted on my way and since I had to flee for safety first, I left my goods and flee for my life. Up till today I don't know what happen to those goods and I am yet to recover from that incident. Every time there is conflict in Uruan, people lost many things and many lives are always taken. Like in the case of Anakpa and Nna-enin in August 2016, a lot of houses and business were destroyed by these same Uruan people and lives were lost. I don't know why people of the same stock should be fighting over things that their fathers died a left for them which they themselves will also die and leave those things one day.*

Another respondent who gave his name as Mr Eka of age 49 years responded that; *We have been losing a lot of people in Uruan to conflicts in recent times. In Anakpa and Nna-enin, we lost a lot of Uruan people and their properties. In fact, they almost burn out their villages. The damages I don't think the people have recover from them. Today, it is Mbiakong. The youths who got involved in terrible acts have brought a lot of damages to Mbiakong people and their neighbours. People have been killed and properties looted. So many people have lost a lot of properties and house in this conflict. I know of one Mr. Eteyen whose son was killed in this conflict. We are tired of conflicts in Uruan Local Government Area. We need peace and government should come and arrest these youths from this community so that we can live in peace again.*

The analysis of data gathered by the researcher through interviews show that Uruan people have suffered a lot of damages in recent communal conflicts (Mbiakong May, 2017). These damages ranged from loss of boats, loss of lives, and loss of businesses to loss of houses.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Data gathered by the researcher through interview show that Uruan Local Government Area in Akwa Ibom State has experience communal conflicts over recent period of time. The Mbiakong conflict is recent communal conflict in Uruan Local Government Area which took place in May, 2017 and it involve many villages in Uruan Local Government Area such as Ifiayong Usuk, Ifia Yong Esuk, Ikot Inyang Esukl, Esuk Odu and Efik people from Cross River State. The researchers gathered from the study participants that the majority of the interviewed participants believed that Mbiakong and other communities in Uruan Local Government Area have suffered many damages through conflict which have hindered community development due to the destructions of people's properties, and

disruption of developmental projects within the area. These damages ranged from loss of boats, loss of lives, and loss of businesses to loss of houses, and as such needs a permanent presence of security operatives in order to maintain peace in the local government area. Findings of the study show that youths are responsible for the communal conflicts in Uruan Local Government Area in Akwa Ibom State. The people of Mbiakong in Uruan Local Government Area have suffered many losses to communal conflicts ranging from loss lives, houses, boats, businesses to domestic animals. These findings give credence to Shedrack (2006) who opined that conflict as a matter of fact, disrupts the process of production, creates conditions for pillage of the communities' resources and diverts their applications from development purposes to serving war. Therefore, conflict is thus responsible for perpetuating misery and underdevelopment in most communities the whole world at large.

CONCLUSION

The researchers, after analysing the data collected confirmed that Uruan youths are responsible for communal conflicts in Uruan Local Government Area, making them the major caused of conflicts in Mbiakong and other communities in Uruan Local Government Area in recent times. The conclusion was based on the result of findings that majority of the study participants who reported that the youths in Uruan are fun of taking arms instead of dialogue during conflicts. In the case of Mbiakong, the youths are said to have taken guns for robbery and raping of market women on the sea. The researchers also gathered that the extent of damages by the Mbiakong people through communal conflicts are enamours and these have in one way or the other hampered community development of Mbiakong community in the Uruan Local Government Area. From the result of the findings, it was confirmed that most of the study participants in their responses agreed that damages due to conflicts in Mbiakong community in Uruan Local Government Area include loss of lives, loss of houses, loss of speed boats, loss of businesses and domestic animals.

RECOMMENDATIONS

From the results of findings and conclusions drawn by the researcher in the study, the researcher derived the following recommendations;

1. The people of Mbiakong in Uruan Local Government Area should see how to use dialogue instead of arms in attaining to conflicting issues among themselves
2. Mbiakong community and the Uruan Local Government Area Youth Council should see how to work out some programmes to engage their youths positively.
3. Mbiakong and other communities in Uruan Local Government Area should partake in security and surveillance toward securing their properties in Uruan Local Government Area against destruction from hoodlums.

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